

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Fashion and Accessories Brand to Increase Brand Awareness and Sales Performance (Case Study: Carbon is Lyfe)

Taajkhansa Najla¹, Prawira Fajarindra Belgiawan²

^{1,2}Institute Technology Bandung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The world of fashion and accessories is now growing quickly. The presence of digital platforms for conducting marketing and promotion of products also supports this development. The growth of this industry presents Carbon is Lyfe, a local men's fashion and accessory brand, with a chance to keep growing. However, Carbon is Lyfe encounters several challenges when growing its business, including low brand awareness and incompletely met sales goals. This study aims to analyze the internal and external environment of the Carbon is Lyfe company, identify the variables influencing customer's brand awareness and purchase intentions for fashion and accessories, and recommend suitable marketing strategies for Carbon is Lyfe. The research method used is qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative methods are used to determine the internal condition of the company and are conducted by interviewing the CEO of Carbon is Lyfe. Meanwhile, quantitative methods are used to determine external business conditions, namely customer analysis, by distributing online questionnaires to the target market of Carbon is Lyfe. The questionnaire results were then processed using the PLS-SEM method using the SMART PLS software. After knowing the internal and external conditions of the Carbon is Lyfe business, the author uses a SWOT and TOWS analysis to formulate appropriate strategies to solve existing problems. As a result of this study, the authors propose five marketing strategies that are suitable for internal and external conditions to increase brand awareness and sales performance of Carbon is Lyfe.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Fashion, Marketing Strategy, Purchase Intention, SWOT Analysis, TOWS.

1. INTRODUCTION

The situation of the world's fashion markets is become more unstable [1]. Fashion products and accessories are still the highest selling products in e-commerce. Based on the survey results from Katadata Insight Center and Kredivo, the number of product transactions reached 22% of total e-commerce shopping throughout 2020 [2]. This proportion is the highest compared to other products sold in e-commerce. Furthermore, based on the 2022 statistics, In the Accessories segment, the number of users is expected to amount to 80.4 million users by 2025. This shows the high potential of the fashion and accessories industry to grow as well as the high competition between fashion and accessory brands. However, based on the data provided by Statista, compared to offline sales, the percentage of fashion and accessories sales through online channels is still relatively low [3]. This shows that there are still challenges to maximize the potential for selling fashion and accessories via online sales channels. It's becoming essential to analyze consumer behavior for fashion goods in online stores. It is interesting to do research because of the dynamics and volatility of the fashion business sector [4].

In growing its business, Carbon is Lyfe faces several challenges. Based on the data, there are still sales targets that have not been fully achieved. Moreover, based on the preliminary research, 87,5% of the respondents still don't know and never heard about Carbon is Lyfe. It means that the brand awareness about Carbon is Lyfe is still low. Therefore, the author wants to formulate the right strategy to increase brand awareness and sales performance of the company.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

PESTLE, Porter's Five Forces, competitive analysis, and customer analysis are examples of tools that can be used for external analysis. To understand the external macroenvironment in which a corporation will function, PEST analysis is a well-known method that is commonly used in business [5]. Another tool used to undertake external analysis of a business is the Porter Five Force, which is made up of five basic forces: threat of new entrants, supplier bargaining power, buyer bargaining power, threat of substitute

products, and industry rivalry [6]. Understanding the behavior of rival businesses and customers is also essential. Competitor analysis influences an organization's strategy and determines how businesses act or react in respective sectors [7].

Internal analysis can be carried out by looking at the marketing mix of the company, segmenting, targeting, and positioning, as well as VRIO analysis. The marketing mix is an effective concept because it makes marketing look accessible, allows for the separation of marketing from other business activities and the delegation of marketing work to specialists, and the components of the marketing mix can have an impact on a company's competitive position [8]. The VRIO approach also helps managers in determining the advantages and disadvantages of their company. More crucially, the framework seeks to benefit from the assets and skills that might raise profitability and competitiveness [9]. Following internal and external analysis, the author does a SWOT and TOWS analysis. Company's strengths and weaknesses are obtained from internal analysis results, while opportunities and threats are obtained from the external analysis. This analysis will be used to formulate suitable marketing strategies for the company.

3. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative and quantitative method are used in this study. In this study, qualitative research was conducted through interviews with the company's CEO. This interview was conducted to obtain in-depth information regarding the internal conditions of the business. Meanwhile, quantitative research was conducted by using online questionnaire to gather information on customer attitudes, especially regarding opinions on the content, sales promotion, advertising, brand interactivity, brand awareness, as well as their intention to make purchases of the company's products. The questionnaire was distributed to 200 customers and potential customers, who are males and at least 17 years old. The data from the questionnaire results were then analyzed by Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) using Smart PLS Software.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In addition to the T statistic, P value can also be used to determine the importance of the association. It is assumed that the equal standard error null hypothesis should be accepted if the p-value is higher than 0.05. One correlation between content quality and brand awareness has a P value greater than 0.05, according to the results of the P value calculation. Based on the calculations for the T statistic and P value in Table 1, we accept the hypotheses H2, H3, H4, and H5, while rejecting H1. Table 2 contains an overview of the results for the hypotheses.

Table 1. PLS-SEM Calculation

Relationship	T statistics	P value
Content Quality → Brand Awareness	0.523	0.601
Sales Promotion → Brand Awareness	6.072	0.000
Advertising → Brand Awareness	3.299	0.001
Brand interactivity → Brand Awareness	2.713	0.007
Brand Awareness → Purchase Intention	10.936	0.000

Table 2. Hypotheses Result

Hypothesis	P value	Conclusion
H1: Content quality has a positive effect on brand awareness	Rejected	Content quality does not have an effect on brand awareness
H2: Sales Promotion has a positive effect on Brand Awareness	Accepted	Sales Promotion has a positive effect on Brand Awareness

H3: Advertising has a positive effect on brand awareness	Accepted	Advertising has a positive effect on brand awareness
H4: Brand interactivity has a positive effect on brand awareness	Accepted	Brand interactivity has a positive effect on brand awareness
H5: Brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention	Accepted	Brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention

A. SWOT

After conducting internal and external analysis, the author proceeds with a SWOT analysis to analyze the strength, weakness, opportunity, and threats of the business.

Strength

1. Offers unique carbon fashion products innovation
2. Brand image as the number one carbon fashion brand in Indonesia

Weakness

1. Have not used appropriate keywords or hashtags for promotional activities
2. There are still many social media features that have not been utilized.

Opportunity

1. Increase in the Current Economic Condition Index
2. The trend of carbon fashion in other countries
3. The increase of social media users in Indonesia
4. The development of digital marketing with influencers
5. The implementation of 5G services
6. Sales promotion can increase people's brand awareness and purchase intention
7. Advertising can increase people's brand awareness and purchase intention
8. Brand interactivity can increase people's brand awareness and purchase intention

Threats

1. Competitors that offer more complete product variants
2. High threats of substitute products

B. Propose Marketing Strategy Based on TOWS Matrix

1. Make virtual try-on

The author proposes that company should use Instagram filters to create virtual try-on for their followers. The AR filter on Instagram has expanded online shopping advertising to increase customer experience. Instagram users can try products through augmented reality filters before adding them to the cart. Carbon is Lyfe can create filters for their bag collections, such as their waist bags, backpacks, and clutch bags, to attract attention and increase public brand awareness. Furthermore, users can share these AR experiences in Instagram stories, and mention Carbon is Lyfe to attract even more people's attention.

2. Create native advertising in collaboration with influencers

The author proposes a solution for Carbon is Lyfe to create native ads. With this strategy, viewers may easily enjoy advertising that blend in with ordinary content and get promotions in it. Instagram videos or photographs that have been shared as part of the content can be used. A day in my Life content created by influencers can also be used for native advertising. In designing this strategy, company can work with male influencers in the fashion sector to create content related to their lifestyle, which includes Carbon is Lyfe products.

3. Offer abandoned cart coupon promotions

The author suggests company to offers coupons to encourage customers to purchase new and more profitable products to increase a business's profit margin. Coupons can build loyalty with existing customers by offering discounts as an incentive to encourage them

to keep shopping at Carbon is Lyfe. In addition, the method of giving coupons must also be made as attractive as possible. Carbon is Lyfe can offer coupons using digital wheel spinner, where customers can play it themselves to win a coupon code. This strategy will increase brand interactivity and become very attractive to customers. The author also proposes a strategy of abandoned cart coupons to be implemented by Carbon is Lyfe. Coupons for abandoned carts are delivered to customers who have put a product in their cart but did not complete the transaction. Sending abandoned cart emails might be a great strategy to boost conversion rates and recoup lost revenue.

4. Offer quantity promotions

The author proposes that Carbon is Lyfe must offer quantity discounts on its products. For instance, if customers purchase one phone case, they will be charged the full price; but if they buy two, they will receive a 20% discount. This strategy may inspire customers to make additional purchases and even invite friends to shop with them at Carbon is Lyfe.

5. Offer bundling package

Bundling occurs when a company packages multiple of their goods or services into one unit, usually at a cheaper cost than they would charge customers to purchase each item separately. To raise the average order value, Carbon is Lyfe must use a bundle strategy, one of which is by providing gift bundles. Gift packages are typically marketed to customers looking for a collection of related goods that would make a thoughtful gift for friends, family, or other loved ones. Carbon is Lyfe can make gift bundle packages in compact and exclusive packaging. This package is suitable as a Father's Day gift, job promotion, or birthday gift.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the internal analysis results, Carbon is Lyfe has several strengths, such as carbon fashion product innovation and a brand image as the number one carbon fashion brand in Indonesia. However, on the other hand, Carbon is Lyfe has weaknesses, such as have not maximized the social media feature yet. Furthermore, based on the results of the external analysis, there are several external factors that become opportunities that can be utilized by the brand, such as the improvement of the current economic condition, the increase in the number of social media users in Indonesia, the trend to follow influencers, the 5G implementation, and the positive effect of sales promotion, advertising, and brand interactivity to brand awareness. However, several external factors pose a threat to Carbon is Lyfe's business, including high threats of substitute products and competitor that offers more products. Moreover, based on customer analysis using PLS SEM, there are several factors positively influence people's brand awareness and purchase intention towards fashion and accessories product, such as: sales promotion, advertising, and brand interactivity. After conducting internal and external analysis and identifying the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the business, the author formulates several solutions to solve business issues, such as:

- Make virtual try-on
- Create native advertising in collaboration with influencers
- Offer abandoned cart coupon promotions
- Offer quantity promotions
- Offer gift-bundling package

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